

Adoption of Drudgery-Reducing Agricultural Tools among Rural Women in Vegetable Cultivation in Haryana

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The study examines the nature of work and contribution of women in the cultivation of vegetables and explores the socio-economic factors influencing the adoption of drudgery-reducing agricultural tools among rural women engaged in vegetable cultivation. A purposive sample of 60 beneficiaries was selected, and data were gathered through structured interviews. Key variables included respondent profile, education, socio-economic status, and mass media exposure. Statistical tools such as percentages, means, and correlation coefficients were used for analysis. Findings revealed that most respondents were under 30 years of age, with a significant portion from backward or scheduled castes. Educational levels were generally low, and income was modest. Active involvement in vegetable cultivation was observed, particularly in harvesting (56%), seed sowing (47%), and land preparation (44%). The most cultivated vegetables included potato, onion, garlic, cucumber, cauliflower, radish, peas, ladyfinger, and tomato. Knowledge assessment revealed the highest awareness for improved serrated sickle and vegetable trolley (Rank I), followed by gloves and mittens (Rank II), vegetable plucker (Rank III), and so on. The study emphasizes the critical role of rural women in agriculture and highlights the need for targeted training and the dissemination of appropriate tools to reduce their labor burden and enhance productivity.

Keywords: Women labour, drudgery, vegetable cultivation, agriculture tools

Agriculture remains the backbone of the Indian economy, employing nearly half of the country's workforce, with women constituting a substantial yet often under-recognized share of agricultural labor. Rural women play a pivotal role in crop production, horticulture, livestock management, and post-harvest operations, particularly in labor-intensive activities such as sowing, weeding, harvesting, and processing (FAO, 2011; Agarwal, 2014). Despite their significant contribution, women's work in agriculture is frequently characterized by drudgery, limited access to resources, and minimal recognition in decision-making processes.

Vegetable cultivation, a vital component of diversified agriculture, offers income generation and nutritional security to rural households. In states like Haryana, vegetable production has expanded due to increasing market demand and government initiatives promoting horticulture. Women are extensively involved

in vegetable cultivation, especially in tasks requiring precision and repetitive manual effort, which often leads to physical strain, fatigue, and long-term health issues (Singh & Vinay, 2018). The predominance of traditional tools and manual methods further exacerbates the drudgery faced by women farmers.

Drudgery in agricultural work refers to the physical and mental strain resulting from monotonous, labor-intensive, and time-consuming tasks performed under challenging environmental conditions (Gite & Agarwal, 2007). Studies have consistently reported that women experience higher levels of drudgery than men due to gender-specific task allocation and ergonomic mismatches between women workers and conventional farm tools (Mehta et al., 2012). Drudgery-reducing agricultural tools, such as improved sickles, vegetable pluckers, gloves, and trolleys, have been developed to enhance work efficiency, reduce physical strain, and improve productivity. However, the adoption of these tools among rural women remains uneven and limited.

Adoption of drudgery-reducing tools is influenced by multiple socio-economic factors, including age, education, caste, income level, access to extension services, training exposure, and mass media participation (Rao, 2016; Kaur & Kaur, 2020). Lack of awareness, inadequate training, financial constraints, and limited availability of women-friendly tools are major barriers hindering widespread adoption. Understanding these factors at the grassroots level is crucial for designing gender-responsive interventions and policies.

Haryana, despite being an agriculturally progressive state, exhibits significant intra-regional disparities in women's access to agricultural technologies. Districts like Panipat and Sonapat represent semi-intensive vegetable-growing areas where women's participation is substantial but largely undocumented. There is a paucity of empirical studies focusing on women's role in vegetable cultivation and their adoption behavior towards drudgery-reducing tools in this region.

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In this context, the present study was undertaken to assess the nature and extent of women's participation in vegetable cultivation and to analyze the socio-economic factors influencing the adoption of drudgery-reducing agricultural tools among rural women in Panipat and Sonipat districts of Haryana. The findings aim to contribute to policy formulation, extension strategies, and capacity-building programs targeted at empowering rural women and improving their occupational well-being and productivity.

Method

The study was conducted during the year 2023-24 in Panipat and Sonipat districts of Haryana, which are known for semi-intensive vegetable cultivation and substantial participation of rural women in agricultural activities.

Participants

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select 60 rural women beneficiaries who were actively engaged in vegetable cultivation. The selection criteria included women's direct involvement in farm operations related to vegetable production, such as land preparation, sowing, weeding, harvesting, and post-harvest activities. The respondents represented diverse socio-economic backgrounds in terms of age, caste, education, income, and level of social participation, ensuring adequate representation for the objectives of the study.

Measure

The study included both independent and dependent variables, measured using appropriate scales and indices. Independent variables comprised respondents' profile characteristics such as age, caste, education, annual income, social participation, socio-economic status, and mass media exposure.

Dependent Variables Included: Nature and extent of women's participation in vegetable cultivation activities, Knowledge level regarding drudgery-reducing agricultural tools and technologies, Adoption level of agricultural tools, Degree of drudgery experienced during various farm operations and socio-economic factors influencing the adoption of drudgery-reducing tools Knowledge, adoption, and drudgery levels were measured using weighted mean scores (WMS), total mean scores (TMS), and ranking techniques based on respondents' responses (Yes/No or High/Medium/Low). Adoption levels were categorized into low, medium, and high based on cumulative scores.

Procedure

Primary data were collected through the personal interview method using a structured interview schedule specifically designed in accordance with the objectives of the study. The interview schedule was pre-tested and refined to ensure clarity, relevance, and reliability of the questions.

The researcher personally visited the selected villages and respondents to establish rapport and ensure accurate data collection. Information was gathered on respondents' socio-economic characteristics, nature and extent of participation in vegetable cultivation, knowledge and adoption of drudgery-reducing agricultural tools, perceived drudgery in various farm activities, and factors affecting the adoption of such tools. Responses were recorded systematically, coded, and later tabulated for analysis.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were coded, classified, and analysed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical tools depending on the nature of the variables. The following statistical techniques were employed such as frequency and percentage to describe socio-economic characteristics and participation levels, mean and standard deviation to assess central tendency and variability, weighted mean score (WMS) and rank order analysis to prioritize tools, activities, and factors, t-test and z-test to examine differences where applicable, Spearman's rank correlation and Pearson's correlation coefficient to study relationships between socio-economic variables and adoption of drudgery-reducing tools The results were interpreted systematically to draw meaningful conclusions in line with the objectives of the study.

Results

Socio-economic Profile of the Women

In Table 1, the socio-economic profile of women is presented. It is revealed that the majority of the women (45.00%) were up to 30 years of age and 30 to 45 years (28.33%). Analysis revealed that almost half of the women (48.33%) hailed from the backward caste and 38.33% from schedule caste. Rest 13.33 per cent of women belonged to the general caste. It was found that 45 per cent of the respondents were educated up to middle level and 40.00 per cent were illiterate. Further study revealed that 46.67 per cent had annual income between Rs. 25,001- Rs. 50,000/- followed by 40.00 per cent with income up to Rs. 25,000/-. These findings align with earlier studies that reported higher participation of younger women from marginalized social groups in labor-intensive agricultural activities due to limited alternative livelihood opportunities (Agarwal, 2014; Mehta et al., 2012). Low educational attainment and poor socio-economic status have been consistently identified as major constraints limiting women's access to information, extension services, and modern agricultural technologies (Rao, 2016).

Data showed from the field that more than three-fifths of the women (65.00%) had no social participation. Nearly fifty percent of the women (48.33%) had a medium level of mass media exposure. Less than two-fifths of women (45.00%) had low socio-economic status, whereas only 13.33 per cent of women had high socio-economic status, respectively. The limited social participation (65%) observed among respondents further restricts women's exposure to collective learning platforms, farmer groups, and self-help organizations, which are known to play a critical role in technology dissemination and empowerment (Singh & Vinay, 2018). Medium levels of mass media exposure among nearly half of the respondents indicate some access to information channels; however, this exposure appears insufficient to translate knowledge into actual adoption, as also reported by Kaur and Kaur (2020).

Nature of Work in Vegetable Cultivation

Table 2 presents the primary information related to the nature of work taken by women and their participation in vegetable cultivation. It is revealed that the majorly cultivated vegetables in Panipat and Sonipat districts were potato, onion, garlic, cucumber, cauliflower, radish, peas, lady finger, tomato, etc. Under land preparation, more than two-fifths of women (44.00%) were involved in ploughing/tilling, in pre-sowing and sowing operations. Activities taken up were sowing of seeds (47.00%) and plant treatment

Table 1*Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents (n=60)*

Sr. No.	Socio-economic variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age		
	Up to 30 years	27	45.00
	30+ to 45 years	17	28.33
	45+ to 60 years	16	26.67
2	Caste		
	General	08	13.33
	Backward	29	48.33
	Schedule	23	38.33
3	Level of education		
	Illiterate	24	40.00
	Up to middle	27	45.00
	Secondary and above	09	15.00
4	Annual income of respondent (Rs.)		
	Up to 25,000/-	24	40.00
	Between 25,001 - 50,000/-	28	46.67
	Above Rs. 50,000/-	08	13.33

5	Social participation		
	No social participation	39	65.00
	Membership in one organization	12	20.00
	Membership in more than one organization	09	15.00
6	Mass media exposure		
	Low	20	33.33
	Medium	29	48.33
	High	11	18.33
7	Socio-economic status		
	Low	27	45.00
	Medium	25	41.67
	High	08	13.33

(24.00%). Other activities were hoeing and weeding (31.00%), drying of vegetables (46.00%), bundling/bagging (45.00%), and field cleaning (36.00%). The activity that was taken by more than fifty percent of women was vegetable harvesting (56.00%). The negligible involvement of women in marketing and transportation activities reflects prevailing gender norms and mobility constraints, which confine women largely to on-farm activities (FAO, 2011; Agarwal, 2014).

Table 2*Nature of Work and Participation of Women in Vegetable Cultivation (n= 60)*

S. N.	Activities	Sub-activities	Response	Percentage
1.	Land Preparation	Field Cleaning	36	60.00
		Ploughing / Tilling	44	73.33
		Farm Yard Manure application	14	23.33
		Forming ridges and furrows	28	46.66
2.	Pre-sowing and sowing operations	Seed treatment	11	18.33
		Sowing of seeds	47	78.33
		Plant treatment	24	40.00
3.	Intercultural Operations	Irrigation (Sprinkler/traditional)	15	25.00
		Hoeing and weeding	31	51.66
		Fertilizer application	15	25.00
		Spraying Pesticide and weedicide	16	26.66
		Fodder collection	26	43.33
4.	Harvesting and Post-Harvesting Operations	Vegetable harvesting	56	93.33
		Drying of vegetables	46	76.66
		Bundling/bagging	45	75.00
		Storage of vegetables	39	65.00
		Marketing/transportation	00	00

Knowledge Regarding Agricultural Tools/Technologies among Women

The data in Table 3 revealed knowledge level of women regarding agricultural tools/technologies used for vegetable cultivation. Based on the weighted mean score calculated from response given by women, Rank I was given to the improved serrated sickle and vegetable trolley, followed by gloves and Mittens (Rank II), vegetable plucker (Rank III), hand ridger (Rank IV), and weeder (Rank V). Rank VI, VII, and VIII were given to the protective kit, cycle hoe, and harvest/cot bag, respectively. Similar observations were made by Mehta et al. (2012), who reported higher awareness of simple, low-cost tools compared to more complex implements.

Adoption of Agricultural Tools/ Technologies by Women

Table 4 presents data related to the adoption of agricultural technologies by women to reduce drudgery. Vegetable trolley (rank I), improved serrated sickle (rank II), vegetable plucker (rank III), hand ridger (rank IV), and Gloves and Mittens (rank V) were the most adopted tools by women. In contrast to that, weeder (rank VI), harvest/cot bag (rank VII), cycle hoe (rank VIII), and personal protective kit (rank IX) were the least adopted tools by women. This knowledge adoption gap has been widely reported in studies on women-friendly agricultural technologies and is often attributed to economic, technical, and socio-cultural barriers (Gite & Agarwal, 2007; Rao, 2016).

Table 3
Knowledge Regarding Agriculture Tools/Technologies (n= 60)

Sr. No.	Tools/Technology	Knowledge		TMS	WMS	Rank
		Yes	No			
1.	Improved Serrated sickle	60	00	120	40.00	I
2.	Vegetable trolley/Basket/Wheelbarrow	60	00	120	40.00	I
3.	Gloves/ mittens	58	02	118	39.33	II
4.	Vegetable Plucker, digger (Bhindi, Potato, etc.)	56	04	116	38.66	III
5.	Hand ridger	55	05	115	38.33	IV
6.	Weeder	44	16	104	34.67	V
7.	Personal protective kit (shoes, hat, apron, goggles, etc.)	35	25	95	31.66	VI
8.	Cycle Hoe	32	28	92	30.67	VII
9.	Harvest/Cot bag	22	38	82	27.33	VIII

Table 4
Adoption of Agriculture Tools/ Technologies by Women (n= 60)

S. N.	Tools/Technology	Adoption		TMS	WMS	Rank
		Adopted	Not Adopted			
1.	Vegetable trolley/Basket/Wheelbarrow	33	27	93	31.00	I
2.	Improved Serrated sickle	32	28	92	30.67	II
3.	Vegetable Plucker, digger (bhindi, potato, etc.), Grafting knife	29	31	89	29.67	III
4.	Hand ridger	28	32	88	29.33	IV
5.	Gloves/ mittens	25	35	85	28.33	V
6.	Weeder	27	28	82	27.33	VI
7.	Harvest/Cot bag	20	40	80	26.67	VII
8.	Cycle Hoe	06	54	66	21.67	VIII
9.	Personal protective kit (shoes, hat, apron, goggles, etc.)	04	56	64	21.33	IX

Table 5
Level of Adoption of Agricultural Technologies (n=60)

S. No	Level	Response
1	Low (6-10)	27 (45.00)
2	Medium (11-15)	25 (41.67)
3	High (15-20)	08 (13.33)

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage

Drudgery Causes Farm Activities

Farm activities undertaken by women in vegetable cultivation are

shown in Table 6. Based on the responses weighted mean score was calculated and activities were ranked in order. Land preparation, manual harvesting, weeding, seed sowing, and plucking/uprooting/de-topping, etc., were activities that were causing most drudgery. In contrast to that, irrigation, carrying dung and produce, and fertilizer application were the activities that were causing the least level of drudgery in vegetable cultivation among women. Similar findings have been reported in earlier ergonomic studies, which identified land preparation, weeding, and harvesting as the most drudgery-intensive operations performed by farm women (Gite & Agarwal, 2007; Singh & Vinay, 2018).

Table 6
Level of Drudgery Caused among Women during Farm Activities (n=60)

S. N.	Farm Activities	High	Medium	Low	TMS	WMS	Rank
1	Land preparation	53	07	0	173	28.83	I
2	Manual Harvesting	41	17	02	159	26.50	II
3	Weeding	19	28	13	126	21.00	III
4	Seed Sowing	34	23	03	151	25.16	IV
5	Plucking/uprooting/de-topping, etc	34	21	05	149	24.83	V
6	Grading and cleaning	31	22	07	144	24.00	VI
7	Bundling and carrying, bagging	17	21	22	115	19.16	VII
8	Vegetable Sapling Transplanting	11	21	28	103	17.16	VIII
9	Irrigation	12	16	32	100	16.66	IX
10	Carrying dung and produce	11	14	25	86	14.33	X
11	Fertilizer application	04	16	40	84	14.00	XI

Socio-economic Factors Affecting the Adoption of Drudgery Reduction Tools

Regarding factors affecting adoption of tools by women in Table 7, more than two-third women reported that tools are expensive (71.67%), complex to use (65.00%), and lack training to operate equipment (65.00%). More than fifty percent were unaware of where to get tools (55.00%), prefer conventional way (53.33%). Only one-fourth mentioned they were not aware of tools, and 10.00 per cent feel tools are not effective. These constraints are consistent with findings of earlier studies that highlighted cost, lack of training, complexity of tools, and preference for traditional practices as major barriers to adoption among farm women (Rao, 2016; Kaur & Kaur, 2020; Lakshmi & Deepika, 2020).

Table 7

Socio-economic Factors Affecting Adoption of Drudgery Reduction Tools (n=60)

Sr. No.	Factors	Frequency	Percentage
1	High prices of tools	43	71.67
2	Uncomfortable/complex to use	39	65.00
3	Lack of training to operate equipments	39	65.00
4	Unaware of where to get tools	33	55.00
5	Prefer the conventional way	32	53.33
6	Less or no subsidy/credit facility for the purchase of equipment	21	35.00
7	Non-availability in the market	18	30.00
8	Not aware of tools	15	25.00
9	Tools are not effective	06	10.00

Summary

The present study provides empirical evidence on the crucial role of rural women in vegetable cultivation and the extent to which drudgery-reducing agricultural tools are adopted in Panipat and Sonipat districts of Haryana. The findings clearly establish that women are actively engaged across all stages of vegetable cultivation, particularly in labor-intensive activities such as land preparation, seed sowing, weeding, and harvesting, which were also identified as the most drudgery-prone operations.

The socio-economic profile of the respondents revealed that a majority were young, belonged to backward or scheduled castes, had low to medium education levels, modest incomes, and limited social participation. These factors significantly influence access to information, resources, and adoption of improved technologies. Although awareness regarding certain drudgery-reducing tools, such as improved serrated sickles and vegetable trolleys, was relatively high, the actual adoption level remained low to medium for most respondents. This gap between knowledge and adoption

highlights structural and behavioral barriers, including the high cost of tools, lack of training, complexity of use, preference for traditional practices, and limited availability in local markets. These findings are in line with earlier research emphasizing that women's empowerment through drudgery-reducing technologies requires integrated technological, institutional, and socio-economic interventions (FAO, 2011; Agarwal, 2014; Rao, 2016).

The persistence of high drudgery levels despite technological interventions underscores the need for a more holistic approach. Strengthening extension services, organizing hands-on training programs, ensuring tool availability at the village level, and promoting subsidized access through government schemes are critical for enhancing adoption. Furthermore, participatory tool development and demonstrations involving rural women can improve acceptability and sustained use. Overall, the study highlights that empowering rural women through appropriate drudgery-reducing tools is not merely a technological issue but a socio-economic and institutional challenge. Addressing these constraints can significantly reduce women's labor burden, improve productivity, and enhance their health and well-being, thereby contributing to inclusive and sustainable agricultural development in Haryana and similar agrarian regions.

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